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Prospects for the Use of the Latest Information Technologies in Combating Environmental Crime

Наукова стаття присвячена дослідженню можливостей сучасних інформаційних технологій у протидії екологічній злочинності. Зокрема, окреслено країні зарубіжні практики використання інновацій у сфері охорони довкілля, проаналізовано окремі організаційно-технічні проблеми в контексті даної тематики, визначено напрямки розвитку та адаптації інформаційних технологій у протидії кримінальним правопорушенням, враховуючи специфіку українського законодавства та практики його застосування. Зроблено висновок, що сучасні технології, включаючи геоінформаційні системи, системи електронного обліку, мобільні додатки для громадськості, автоматизовані системи відстеження викидів, безпілотні літальні апарати та інші інноваційні рішення здатні забезпечити прозорість діяльності підприємств та активне залучення громадян до процесу контролю, дозволять оперативно реагувати на порушення, суттєво підвищити ефективність дій правоохоронних органів України, зокрема, у протидії екологічній злочинності.

Ключові слова: *довкілля, кримінальні правопорушення, протидія, інформаційні технології, інновації.*

The scientific publication is dedicated to researching the possibilities of modern information technologies in combating environmental crime. In particular, individual organizational and technical problems in the context of this topic were analyzed, the best foreign practices of using innovations in the field of environmental protection were outlined, directions for the development and adaptation of information technologies in the detection and investigation of criminal offenses were determined, taking into account the specifics of Ukrainian legislation and the practice of its application, to ensure sustainable and harmonious development of the country's ecological security. Analysis of the experience of countries such as the USA, Great Britain, Germany and Canada has proven the impact of the latest technologies on the effectiveness of detecting and countering criminal offenses against the environment. It was concluded that modern technologies, including geo-information systems, electronic accounting systems, mobile applications for the public, automated emissions tracking systems, unmanned aerial vehicles and other innovative solutions are able to ensure the transparency of enterprises' activities and the active involvement of citizens in the control process, will allow prompt response to violations, to significantly increase the effectiveness of the actions of law enforcement agencies of Ukraine, in particular, in collecting evidence of illegal activities in the field of the environment. It was emphasized that taking into account the current environmental challenges in our country and the requirements for increasing the efficiency of law enforcement activities, the introduction and improvement of relevant innovative technologies in the field of environmental protection is urgent and expedient. This will not only improve the effectiveness of combating criminal offenses against the environment but will also stimulate the appropriate attitude of business to environmental standards, while strengthening the public's trust in the actions of power structures.

Keywords: *environment, criminal offenses, counteraction, investigation, information technologies, innovations.*

Target setting. In the conditions of modern digital society and rapid technological progress, methods of achieving criminal results are being

improved. Under such circumstances, traditional methods of combating crime no longer meet the needs of modern theory and practice, which

necessitates the search for innovative means of combating criminal offenses at the international and national levels.

Criminal offenses against the environment cover a wide range of activities, from illegal deforestation and water pollution to illegal hunting of animals and illegal trade in natural resources. Taking into account the high level of organization and technical equipment of "ecological" criminals, primarily in the field of forest and subsoil use, there is a need to find innovative means of combating crime, which involves the application of modern achievements of digital, technological and scientific and technical progress. In particular, based on the clarification of trends in environmental crime, we see the need to determine the prospects for the use of modern information and search systems and technologies (geographical information system technologies (hereinafter - GIS technologies), unmanned aerial vehicles (hereinafter - UAVs), electronic systems and mobile applications) in counteracting and preventing illegal actions against the environment, etc.

The criminological principles of the use of information and search systems and other information technologies for the prevention of crime consist in the use by the subjects of preventive activities in the system of measures at the national, special criminological and individual levels of modern information and communication technologies for the purpose of collecting, storing, analyzing criminologically significant information, forecasting crime and counteracting the processes of its determination, resocialization of potential criminals [1, p. 67].

Therefore, balanced protection of the environment and combating criminal offenses in the specified area have become urgent tasks, without solving which it is difficult to guarantee well-being and sustainable development in the future. In the conditions of active processes of Ukraine's entry into the European community [2, p. 96], the mentioned circumstances indicate the expediency of determining the prospects of using the latest information technologies in combating environmental crime.

Analyses of research and publications. The work of such scientists as: S.B. Havrysh, A.P. Hetman, O.M. Dzhezha, O.L. Dubovik, A.P. Zakalyuk, O.M. Kostenko, O.P. Lytvyn, V.K. Matviychuk, V.O. Navrotskyi, V.L. Ortynskyi, Yu.A. Turlova, V.I. Shakun and others. However, the specific question regarding the use of modern information technologies in combating criminal offenses against the

environment from a criminological point of view is not fully resolved, some practical aspects of the application of innovations in the specified field remain open for scientific discussion.

The purpose of the article is a comprehensive and thorough review and analysis of foreign experience in the implementation and use of innovative technologies, methods and techniques of law enforcement agencies countering criminal offenses against the environment and an assessment of the possibility of its implementation in the Ukrainian context.

The statement of basic materials. In combating crime against the environment, the role of law enforcement institutions is extremely important. It is they who ensure compliance with environmental legislation and respond to violations in the specified area. The main areas of activity of law enforcement agencies in countering criminal offenses against the environment should include: investigation of criminal offenses (gathering of evidence, identification of guilty persons, organized criminal groups involved in illegal acts, etc.); cessation of illegal activities that cause damage to the environment (removal of illegally extracted resources, cessation of polluting activities, etc.); prevention of crime against the environment (training and information activities for the public and enterprises, institutions, organizations, implementation of preventive measures, cooperation with environmental organizations, etc.); cooperation with other bodies and international organizations (environmental agencies, public organizations), mutual exchange of information on the state of the environment; monitoring and reporting on the implementation of environmental norms and standards.

The effectiveness of law enforcement agencies in the detection and investigation of criminal offenses against the environment depends on a number of internal and external factors related to: legislation and policy, funding and resources, qualifications and professional training, the level of interaction with other institutions, applied technologies and equipment.

In the conditions of modern digital society and rapid technological progress, modernized means and methods of collecting and recording evidence and other information important for the investigation are gaining more and more popularity. This situation is caused by one leading factor - efficiency. In particular, innovative processes are also reflected in the activities of domestic law enforcement agencies.

However, such development is not always harmonious, since in practice a wider range of means and methods for collecting and investigating evidence can be used than described in the domestic forensic theory [3, p. 651].

An analysis of advanced foreign practices in the use of innovative products and technologies will help to understand exactly which aspects can be obstacles in the detection and investigation of criminal offenses against the environment, and which measures can be taken to improve the efficiency of law enforcement agencies in this area. After all, modern innovative technologies and equipment have become an integral part of the activities of law enforcement agencies in the fight against criminal offenses against the environment in various countries.

In the USA, a distinctive feature of the criminological model of combating crime is the recognition of the crucial role of the police and criminal law control over crime [4, p. 13], innovative technologies and equipment are actively used at various levels - from local police to federal agencies. In particular, the capabilities of GIS technologies in the activities of law enforcement agencies and environmental agencies of the USA are actively used to detect illegal logging, illegal dumping of waste and other violations of environmental legislation.

In some regions of Great Britain, police departments and local authorities have stepped up the use of mobile applications to help citizens report various violations, including environmental ones. They have become an additional channel of communication between the police and the community, which allows for prompt response to problems and maintaining transparency. This initiative proved to be very effective, after which it allowed citizens to actively cooperate with law enforcement agencies in detecting and responding to environmental violations. Implementation of such technologies improves transparency and increases citizens' trust in authorities. Also, the British organization Environment Agency uses automated systems for measuring the level of pollution of air and water sources, and individual police units in the UK implemented mobile applications that allowed citizens to send photos and information about possible environmental violations.

Canada's water management sector uses distributed water monitoring systems to measure water quality and detect violations. Electronic reporting systems have also been introduced in Canada for enterprises with emissions of harmful substances,

which help in effective control of their activities.

One of the countries that actively develops and implements the latest technologies to ensure ecological stability and reduce the impact on the environment is Germany. An electronic transport monitoring system is used in this country to detect violations of environmental regulations, such as exceeding emission levels. In addition, businesses in Germany must keep electronic records of emissions and resource use, which allows monitoring of their activities. Electronic emission accounting systems and technological resources of this country, such as electronic registers, automated tracking, data standardization, play an important role in ensuring transparency and control over the environmental activities of companies. The specified accounting systems are part of Germany's national strategy for preserving the environment and supporting sustainable development. Their success is based on a combination of technological innovation, active control by authorities and public involvement.

It is worth noting that currently in Ukraine, relevant programs and projects are already being used (Police Online, electronic petitions, etc.), which stimulate the use of mobile applications to facilitate interaction between citizens and law enforcement agencies, in particular in the fight against crime against the environment. At the same time, it is important to understand that the effective implementation of such projects requires not only the development and implementation of a mobile application, but also the correct organization of work with data, ensuring user privacy, as well as constant support and updating of programs.

Determining the role of GIS technologies, it should be noted that they allow the collection, analysis and visualization of geospatial information, which helps law enforcement officers effectively combat environmental violations. Initial information about the state of the environment and its possible violation is obtained from various sources - satellite images, aerial photography, etc. Satellite systems enable high-precision monitoring of nature reserves and forests. GIS uses satellite image data to determine changes in forest cover and identify possible illegal activities. The collected information is converted into a digital format, and digital maps are created based on it, which contain information about forest areas, water sources, ecologically sensitive areas, and others.

In addition, GIS allows you to analyze digital

maps and identify differences between the current state of the environment and legal requirements. Violations such as illegal logging or illegal waste dumping can be identified on digital maps. In addition, these systems are used for planning patrol routes and monitoring. The use of satellite systems allows law enforcement officers to effectively bypass and control large territories, remotely monitor and further analyze landscape complexes, relevant nature conservation areas, areas, forest masses and water bodies in order to detect unauthorized logging, pollution of water bodies, and other illegal effects on the environment.

Environmental organizations and activists in Ukraine use GIS and computer imagery to detect and document environmental violations that must monitor compliance with environmental standards. The fight against environmental violations depends on the cooperation of various structures and the use of modern technologies, in particular GIS and satellite technologies, for effective monitoring and disclosure of violations of environmental legislation in Ukraine.

Law enforcement agencies collect and integrate various sources of information, such as video surveillance, mobile data, automatic license plate recognition systems and other sensors. The specified information can be presented on geographical maps and used to determine the location of the violator. The use of GIS allows predicting possible damage locations and responding to them promptly. Heat maps determine zones of increased activity of violators or zones where offenses are committed. GIS can also be used for the joint work of various law enforcement agencies and environmental protection organizations, which allows for the coordination of actions and the exchange of important information.

UAVs occupy a special place among modern robotic complexes and innovative technologies. They can be effectively used by law enforcement agencies in the fight against crime. This is primarily due to their wide functionality, which makes it possible to combine the automatic piloting system in real time with the simultaneous acquisition and transmission of forensically significant information using modern equipment of navigation systems, aerial photography and video recording (multispectral, magnetic, large-scale surveying, photogrammetry and etc.), video monitoring, mapping, 3-D modeling, analysis of harmful substances in the air, infrared and thermal imaging survey of the area, premises, etc. [5, p. 9].

Due to their capabilities, UAVs have become a tool in the fight against environmental violations and the preservation of the environment in many leading democracies. Among other things, they are used to prevent the commission of criminal and administrative offenses [6, p. 273]. Their use is possible during inspection of places of illegal cutting of forest plantations, for monitoring waste discharges, patrolling nature reserves, and documenting the state of the environment. For example, in the USA, such systems are actively used at various levels - from local police to federal agencies.

The use of UAVs in ecological monitoring and environmental protection has significant advantages. These aircraft can quickly fly over large areas and hard-to-reach places, which allows for effective control of nature reserves and large forest strips. UAVs are equipped with video cameras and other sensors, which allows you to save high-quality data to identify possible damage and detect illegal activities in the field of the environment.

Therefore, modern technologies such as satellite imaging, GIS, UAVs, electronic systems and mobile applications play an increasingly important role for law enforcement agencies in the detection and investigation of environmental crimes. They help to improve monitoring, collection and analysis of data, contribute to the documentation and conduct of separate investigative (search) actions aimed at obtaining evidentiary information, etc. [7, p. 50]. In Ukraine, as well as in other countries, the mentioned technological tools should become a common tool for tracking violators in the field of environment, detection of illegal emissions, illegal cutting of forests, damage to water resources, etc.

It should be noted that Ukrainian law enforcement agencies are gradually implementing certain elements of the Intelligence-Led Policing (ILP) model - a model of law enforcement activity guided by analytical intelligence. In particular, analytical work uses: operational analysis (telephone call data analysis, analysis of criminal groups, case analysis, comparative analysis); tactical analysis (criminal analysis, analysis of criminal trends, geospatial analysis, analysis of places of concentration of crime, temporal analysis, criminal models, profiles of suspects/victims); strategic analysis (SWOT analysis, PEST analysis, analysis of crime models/forms and profiling, trend analysis, analysis using geographic profiling); analysis of data from open sources

(OSINT); analysis of data from many sources (MultiSource Analysis).

As modern scholars rightly point out, although ILP originated as a strategy to combat complex crime, complex crimes such as terrorism and organized crime, information sharing and analytical activities can be applied to many problems faced by the police, similarly to a problem-oriented strategy police activity [8, p. 505].

It is natural that the specified evolutionary process of ILP implementation requires a lot of time and a systematic approach, taking into account advanced foreign practices. Studies studying the functions of crime analysts in law enforcement agencies indicate a lack of communication between analysts and end users of analytical products [9, p. 147-168]. At the same time, scientists point to the problem of understanding the role of information, analysis and analytical intelligence in its use in practical activities [10, p. 190-191]. Therefore, it is worth emphasizing that the use of information and the application of analytical processes in units must be preceded by the development of clear, understandable and reliable mechanisms that will enable the provision of appropriate analytical potential and access to information and analytical products. This will expand the possibilities of using analytical products as a result of information and analytical activities in combating criminal offenses against the environment.

Conclusions. Criminal offenses against the environment pose a serious threat to the sustainable

development of society and the preservation of the environment, requiring highly effective and innovative approaches to countering crime in this area. In this context, the key role belongs to high-tech innovative technologies. They provide the ability to collect, analyze and use large volumes of data related to the state of the environment and the detection of criminal activities. Modern data analysis tools and information technologies simplify the disclosure and investigation of criminal offenses in the field of the environment, contributing to the determination of the amount of illegal impact on environmental objects, the identification of persons involved in the commission of the specified illegal acts.

The expediency of using advanced foreign practices in this area is beyond doubt, because many countries have developed and successfully use modern technologies for combating environmental crime - environmental monitoring, software for detecting criminal offenses, ILP, GIS, BpLA, etc. The implementation of information technologies in combating environmental crime has great potential in increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of combating criminal offenses in the field of the environment, thereby contributing to the preservation of the environment and ensuring sustainable development for future generations.

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